

Synthesis of some 1-Aroyl-3-methyl-4-substituted-phenyl-6-imino-4,7-dihydro-1,3-thiazino[5,4-d]pyrazoles as Pesticides

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1-Aroyl-3-methyl-4-substituted-phenyl-6-imino-4,7-dihydro-1,3-thiazino[5,4-d]pyrazoles (3) have been synthesised by the condensation of 1-aryl-4-arylideno-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (2) and thiourea in methanolic potassium hydroxide. The compounds have been screened for their fungicidal activities against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* and antibacterial activities against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*.

In continuation of our work on fused heterocycles, we report here the synthesis of another system 1,3-thiazino[5,4-d]pyrazole and evaluate their anti-fungal and antibacterial properties.

Reaction of aroyl hydrazide with ethyl acetoacetate gave the corresponding aroyl-3-methyl- Δ^2 -pyrazolin-5-one (1) by the reported method of Pathak¹. Condensation of 1 with araldehyde under the Knoevenagel conditions furnished compounds 2, which on refluxing with thiourea and potassium hydroxide gave the titled compounds 3 (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at 60 MHz. Acid hydrazides were prepared by reported method².

1-Aroyl-3-methyl- Δ^2 -pyrazolin-5-ones (1): The aroyl hydrazide (0.1 mol) was heated with ethyl acetoacetate (0.1 mol) for 4 h and the resulting solid was isolated from aqueous alcohol: (R=H), 70%, m.p. 62°; ν_{\max} 1 620 (C=N), 1 710 and 1 640 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.0–8.2 (5H, m, ArH) and 4.2 (2H, s, CH₂CO).

1-Aroyl-4-arylideno-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (2): To compound 1 dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added fused sodium acetate (0.015 mol) and araldehyde (0.01 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. It was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol: (R=R'=H), 68%, m.p. 178° (Found: C, 74.36; H, 5.00; N, 9.41. C₁₈H₁₄N₂O₂ requires C, 74.48, H, 4.82, N, 9.65%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 690, 1 640 (C=O) and 1 620 (C=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.6 (1H, s, CH) and 7.3–8.0 (10H, m, ArH). Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3*

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	H	4-OCH ₃	182	69
2b	2-Cl	4-OCH ₃	172	71
2c	4-Cl	4-Cl	222	67
2d	2,4-Cl ₂	4-OCH ₃	214	69
2e	2,4-Cl ₂	4-Cl	197	67
3a	H	4-OCH ₃	204	70
3b	2-Cl	4-OCH ₃	272	69
3c	4-Cl	4-Cl	218	67
3d	2,4-Cl ₂	4-OCH ₃	242	64
3e	2,4-Cl ₂	4-Cl	187	67

*All compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

1-Aroyl-3-methyl-4-substituted-phenyl-6-imino-4,7-dihydro-1,3-thiazino[5,4-d]pyrazolones (3) †

A mixture of **2**, thiourea (0.011 mol) and KOH (0.02 mol) was refluxed in methanol for 2–3 h. On cooling, it was acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from rectified spirit: (R=R'=H), 68%, m p. 216° (Found: C, 65.37; H, 4.51; N, 16.03. C₁₉H₁₆N₄OS requires: C, 65.51; H, 4.59; N, 16.09%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 560 (NH), 3 410 (=NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 1 610, 1 500 and 1 460 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.7 (1H, s, S-CH), 7.3–7.9 (10H, m, ArH) and 9.5 (2H, s, NH). Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

Pesticidal screening: Compounds **2** and **3** were screened for their antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* using agar-growth technique³ at concentrations of 1000, 750 and 500 mg dm⁻³ and the percentage of inhibition noted after 96 h. The most active compound of this investigation was **3d**, which has nearly comparable activity with that of commercial fungicide Carbendazim tested under similar

conditions. Other compounds showed moderate activities.

The antibacterial activity was determined by Vincent and Vincent filter paper disc technique⁴ at concentrations of 1000, 750 and 500 mg dm⁻³ against *S. aureus* and *S. subtilis* and the percentage of inhibition was noted after 24 h. Compounds **2** and **3** showed moderate activities against both the fungi.

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